

GGOS Portal Survey

Results

July 2023

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1. Introduction

1.1 GGOS-Portal Introduction

The services of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG) provide very important and valuable geodetic data, information, and data products that are increasingly relevant for Earth System research, including monitoring of global change phenomena and a wide range of diverse applications such as satellite navigation, surveying, mapping, engineering, geospatial information systems, and so on.

Currently, it is difficult for many people to obtain an overview of all available geodetic products and data. The Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS) of the IAG aims to fill this gap by developing the GGOS-Portal, which will serve as a **unique search and access point for geodetic data and products** (one-stop shop). Data and products will be described by detailed metadata and remain physically located at their originating data centers of each contributing IAG service and other data providers. The GGOS-Portal will only synchronize the provided metadata and include it in its platform to ensure better discoverability. In the long term, the GGOS-Portal can provide a set of tools for organized knowledge search, including visualization to support identification and selection of appropriate resources (information, data, products).

In general, geodetic data portals are a dime a dozen. However, the GGOS portal will be much more than just a data portal for geodetic data from the IAG Services. The **combination of the easy understandable descriptions** of products and observation techniques with this comprehensive source of **detailed geodetic metadata** makes the future GGOS portal unique.

Prominent **examples for existing Metadata Portals** are the GEOSS-Portal, the GNSS Metadata Portal Europe, the EPOS: GNSS Product Portal Europe and the Metadata Information System at BKG, Germany.

1.2 What are Metadata and DOI's for Geodetic Data?

Metadata is data that provides information about the actual data, but not its content.

How does Metadata look like? - Metadata of geodetic data and products can contain **several types of information**. That can consist of general descriptions like **title, data format, version, date, link to the data, contact person, ...** and of detailed descriptions like **antenna type, receiver type, analyzing method, used models, ...**

What are Metadata Standards? - To **make metadata comparable** it is beneficial to use common metadata standards / schemas such as a simple Sitelog, GeodesyML, ISO19115, Dublin Core Format, etc.

How can Metadata be provided? - Geodetic metadata can be **made available in the internet** via various ways: That could be a **simple website** where the geodetic data is described. In this case it is favorable to provide the metadata in a **machine-readable format** (e.g. XML or JSON). This is used, for example, for DOI metadata or GeodesyML. Another way is to provide a **metadata file** (e.g. *.txt, *.log, Sitelog, ...) on a server which can be accessed via (S)FTP or HTTP(S) request. A provision of metadata by **standardized Interfaces** or **API** is also possible. There are several standards in use (e.g. OAI-PMH interface, RESTful interface, OGC web feature service, ...). This allows easy synchronization (harvesting) of metadata for metadata portals like the GGOS Portal.

What are DOI's for Geodetic Data? - To make geodetic data and products **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)** it is advantageous to assign DOI (Digital Object Identifier) for them (e.g. <http://doi.org/10.5880/ICGEM.2019.011>). This allows **citability and scientific recognition**. Looking more closely at DOIs for geodetic data, they consist of metadata provided in a **standardized metadata schema** and available on a **website (landing page)** that is also machine-readable (e.g., XML format). If you want to read more, please visit the page of the GGOS Committee on DOI's for geodetic Data Sets.

1.3 Survey – General Information

GGOS conducted a survey from April to March 2023 to inquire the opinions of geodetic data users on data availability and visibility and to identify requirements for a comprehensive and user-friendly GGOS Portal. In addition GGOS obtained an overview of the current availability of data products and their metadata.

Survey Link: ggos.org/portal

Survey period: **April to March, 2023**

Total Participants: **195** (from 57 countries)

Objective - Get overview about:

- **Geodetic data usage** (user, producer, provider)
- **Provision of Metadata and DOI's** for geodetic data
- **Opinion about a GGOS-Portal** and needed functions

1.4 Survey – Participants Statistics

Total Participants: **195** (from 57 countries)

PARTICIPANTS PER COUNTRY

PARTICIPANTS PER CONTINENT

GGOS Portal Survey 2023 - Results

2. Survey Results

2.1 Availability of Geodetic Data and Products

Question: In your experience, is it easy to find geodetic data and products?

Question: Where would you mainly start to search for geodetic data or products?

Question: **Do you agree that a central point of access for geodetic data and products is missing to improve discoverability and should be established in the future GGOS-Portal?**

2.2 Specific Questions about the future GGOS-Portal

Question: **What would be a great benefit of a future GGOS-Portal?**

- Have a **central access point** for geodetic data and products.
- Get a clear **overview** of all available geodetic data and products.
- **Geodetic data and products** become **more visible**.
- The **importance of the IAG and Geodesy** as a whole becomes **more visible**.

Open Question: **In your opinion, are there any other benefits?**

“Yes, interest in making use of that topic”

“would easily build up connections among geodetic data and products”

“To avoid duplication in data”

“standardized procedure to get data DOIs and of referencing data”

“to make measurement techniques and data utilization more widely known”

“Push any kind of applications (scientific, public, private)”

“Provide geodetic data users with a friendly environment to access each and every relevant/reliable source.”

“The availability of updated geodetic information.”

“It would support greater visibility of freely available data and, hopefully, encourage broader sharing of data for owners not willing to share. Some Nations place restrictions on data sharing. Additionally, this may also have the same effect as ERS-1 did on GEOSAT - once data is publicly available, other more restrictive data may also be released.”

“Interaction (exchangeability) with internal (IAG Services) and external portal (e.g., GEOSS, ...); Improved visibility of geodetic data (e.g., society, policy-makers, ...)”

“Help networking of stakeholders related to geodesy”

“Have more users of our geodetic products, including users in scientific disciplines not directly associated with geodesy”

“have a central access point to find information about community governance and different entities/actors”

“Geodetic data should be findable and hopefully, sufficient metadata is available as well as reference papers publications, etc. related to the data production.”

“From my perspective, the data and products are already easy to find. I don't see a lot of benefit in a portal just for that reason. For other things, like a software repository to read/use data and products, a centralized location could be quite valuable.”

“Environment Sciences will enjoy of this data distribution.”

“The user saves time to get the data and has more reliability about its origin and quality.”

“Efficiency. Discoverability.”

“easy availability of geodetic data will spur research and innovation.”

“Ease in database management and maintenance”

“Better communication between all involved parties.”

“Acknowledging and showcasing the work conducted by researchers and data providers”

“A redundant database to CDDIS will support operational needs”

Question: **Which user groups should be addressed by the GGOS-Portal?**

Question: **Which geodetic data and products should be accessible via the GGOS-Portal?**

- Data from **IAG** components (e.g. Services).
- Other **non-IAG** geodetic research products derived from geodetic data.
- Data from **space agencies** (e.g. ESA, NASA) relevant to Geodesy.
- Densified geodetic data on a **regional or national level** (e.g. from mapping agencies).

Open Question: **In your opinion, should other types of data be available at the GGOS-Portal?**

"The key thing is to focus on one type of data/services and to do it extremely well. Bad portals try to do too much."

"Some comments on the answers above: Concerning non-IAG products and data from space agencies, the data providers should be asked for permission before making their data accessible through the GGOS portal. A meaningful selection of potential data and products could be useful to avoid an overload of the GGOS portal. This holds in particular for densified geodetic data on a regional or national level."

"Products non-derived but needed for geodetic analyses (ex. mapping functions or ocean loading models) and also the data's standards information (ex. sinex files, rinex)"

"Probably geodetic data provided by private companies such as private CORS"

"Links to other data repositories, portals, clearinghouses etc. housing geodetic and geophysical related data."

"It is not clear to me if you gonna host data and products in an independent data center or if you just collect metadata from data centres and make those links available. Otherwise all of the above is needed."

"I suggest to think of an Internet Services that connect existing data repositories"

"Geodetic products derived at individual institutions"

"Data products from minorities and singular researchers could be added"

"Data products are desirable"

"Studies of tectonic square movement, Weather forecasting studies, Satellite measurement techniques, Gravimetric calculations (absolute and relative).

"Rapid Service/Prediction of Earth Orientation"

"TIGA, regional densification efforts (SIRGAS, EUREF, AFREF, APREF, etc), tilt measures, subsidence measures,"

"Standardized academic data"

"Products should include coordinate and EOP time series, orbits and clocks, and raw data from different techniques."

"EOP Combinations, Predictions, and relevant models contributing to data products"

"Daily and 5-minute (e, n, u) coordinate and integrated water vapor time series from all available geodetic GNSS stations in the world. Quality assurance data for each daily RINEX file."

"CRS data from EPSG.org etc."

"Auxiliary data/models required in the computation of geodetic products (e.g. solar radio flux), at least linked if not directly stored."

Question: **How should it be possible to search for geodetic data in the GGOS-Portal?**

- Search by **spatial selection** (on an interactive dynamic map)
- Search by **temporal selection** (setting requested time period on a timeline)
- Search by **API request** to GGOS-Portal

Question: **What functionalities should the GGOS-Portal offer?**

- **Informing users about related products** on the search results page
- Including **easy-to-understand descriptions** of products and observing techniques (as currently available on ggos.org) on the GGOS-Portal.
- **Attractive visualization** of selected geodetic data and products (interactive graphs, charts, ...)
- **Exchangeability**: Make GGOS-Portal metadata available for other portals as well (e.g. GEOS)

Open Question: **Do you think the GGOS-Portal should have further important functionalities?**

“User friendly links based on spatial and temporal selection and a simple visualization would be ideal.”

“To link to a resource system related to the data type for tutorial, tools, code snippets etc”

“The portal should do data discovery first, then simple data visualization (so users know if data is what they need), then data download. Real time download is a benefit.”

“some statistics for data providers would be nice”

“Most important is to make it *easy* for data/products providers to participate, even at basic levels, as it is discovery and access to the providers' data/products that is most important. All the above are "nice to have", but some providers will already have their own selection tools (interactive maps), so this is not essential from the start. Some users will simply discover their favorite providers and then go directly to them.”

“Links and mention to the origin of data. Information about licenses of use. Easy access and download through automatic scripts (some users can use these data daily in automatic processings)”

“Is a "data portal" of benefit for users, or would a further step (much higher ambition) be a "geodesy data lab" which includes analysis functionality?”

“Instead of hosting the data providing links to existing archives (CDDIS, EPOS ...) might be very beneficial.”

“Good Search engine optimization: Catalogues should be searchable and understandable by search engines, so they will land high in search results. Also consider community forums and a community driven place to provide tutorials and data processing recipes”

“GGOS may not have all the data but GGOS must have 'links' etc. to ALL data...”

“To make known the methodology for the exchange of metadata of the GGOS portal with other portals.”

“Cater for the novice and the expert”

“A software code repository to help in building tools for reading the various formats of data and products would be very useful.”

“(short term) permalink if temporal and spatial selection from a map; (long term) extraction tool to download data from the selection when most of the data are interoperable”

Question: **How detailed should the metadata descriptions be in the GGOS-Portal?**

Question: **What would be a major challenge in realizing the GGOS-Portal?**

- Make the GGOS-Portal **user friendly**
- Non-existence of metadata (or DOIs) and **encouraging these data provider** to create and maintain metadata (and DOI's) for their data and products.
- **Maintenance and long-term availability** of the GGOS-Portal

Open Question: **Do you have other challenges in mind?**

"Web application security"

"User friendly links to existing resources should be strongly preferred over new archives and/or extra requirements."

"To get potential users to find the GGOS-Portal."

"To create and provide correlation between datasets with different origin"

"standard API for automated data search and retrieval"

"Speed of technological advancement"

"Obtaining legacy data."

"Multiplicity of providers. Provider unwillingness to make data available in a centralised location (feel ownership threatened, loss of control and information on number of users/downloads/purposes which may be required for funding bodies -> needs clear credits, links, info and documentation as required by providers; providers should be able to access reports on data downloads and data usage forms if required)."

"Many users of geodetic data use their own download scripts to D/L their data daily (or even subdaily). While this may not be a primary issue for a future GGOS portal, it should be kept in mind, that an automatic data download will be possible"

"Make it possible for automatic download of data"

"Maintain focus on encouraging participation as the most important aspect, rather than application of specific standards. Implement mechanism for user feedback to the portal and data/products providers."

"INTEROPERABILITY OF DATA SHARED ON THE PORTAL BY DIFFERENT AGENCIES"

"information and best practices tend to age quickly so we need curators that remain engaged with the different scientific communities (papers, conferences, workshops, etc) so that the public information in the new portal remains relevant and engaging"

"Feature bloat. A key step is to hire a user interface designer before starting the project, and to have them participate in all planning, design, and testing."

"Everything is nice to have, but I am slightly doubtful about the cost-effectiveness."

"Data formats"

"continuous collaboration and commitment of the different institutions"

"challenging to have as many geodetic datasets as possible, but keeping them organized and easy to find"

"Challenge in motivating data provider to have their data/products in the portal. Will they be visible and get "credit" for their data?"

"avoid duplication and guarantee interoperability and consistency"

2.3 Interaction with Geodetic Data & Products – User, Producer, Provider

Question: **How do you interact with geodetic data and products?**

Questions to User of Geodetic Data

Question: **Which category best describes what you use geodetic observation data and products for?**

Question: **How often are you using geodetic data?**

Questions to Producer/Provider of Geodetic Data

Question: **Which kind of geodetic data are you producing / providing?**

Question: **What observation techniques are used for your data?**

Question: In which category can your products be assigned?

Question: How often is your data changing or get updates?

2.4 Usage of Metadata for Geodetic Data

Questions: **Do you provide metadata (standardized descriptions, links) for your geodetic data/products?**

If no: **Do you plan to create metadata for your geodetic data/products in future?**

If yes (providing metadata): **How do you make your metadata available in the Internet?**

If providing metadata and selected “Other” in the questions before: **Please specify the used standardized interface or API which you are using.**

If providing metadata: **Which metadata standard / schema do you use?**

If providing metadata: **How often do you update your metadata content?**

If providing metadata: **Are you interested in making your metadata available (synchronized) on the future GGOS-Portal?**

2.5 Usage of DOI for Geodetic Data

Questions: **Do your geodetic data/products have DOI's (Digital Object Identifier)?**

If no: **Are you interested in creating DOIs for your data to make it more discoverable and citable?**

If no: **Why are you not currently using DOI's for your geospatial data?**

2.6 Open Answers

Question: **Do you have any other comments?**

"Why I am a bit hesitant concerning data DOIs: for me (or let's say, for the university), it is more important that the related publications are cited. I would happily provide the DOIs of the related papers though. In general, the GGOS Portal is a good initiative and I would be happy to share our data/products."

"we need a catalogue of the data and products of the IAG services, described by harmonized metadata (including DOI and related IDs for producers, funding organization, etc). Findable with filters that could be based on geodetic variables (and not only technics, satellite missions, ...) + Geographical and temporal selections on a map. Accessible with standard protocols (ftp, https, opendap, wms, ...). Visualisation tools could be nice too (map, charts, ...)."

"We do have a portal for our combined monthly Earth gravity models (ICGEM), but in our experience, it is still not well known among potential users (hydrologists, glaciologists, climate research) and a central GGOS portal would most probably be beneficial."

"We believe that having a common portal for accessing geodetic data would be very useful. However, data should be officially stored and maintained by the responsible services/providers only, to avoid misalignment and to preserve the services' role. This is an important matter from our side."

"We already had additional products that we intend to share with the community in the near future (e.g., multi-year time series of multi-GNSS GPS+GLONASS+Galileo+BDS, multi-frequency, STEC and VTEC tracks and maps, reprocessed, involving 480+ GNSS stations and 100+ satellites), but we are reluctant to do so at the moment because there is no reliable way for the external user to acknowledge us as the data center behind these products (i.e., there are no related article, and there is no DOI associated to the data set...)."

"An excellent idea"

"Two sites that might be useful to compare and take ideas from: <https://gnssdata-epos.oca.eu/#/site> <https://gnssproducts.epos.ubi.pt/>"

"This is a timely survey. Thanks a million for doing this."

"This is a good idea - I'm interested in how this portal will link / integrate to other space geodetic data centres rather than duplicating the data and creating another global data centre. i.e. For a particular IGS station you can pull up a metadata record that says the data for this day is available from CDDIS, GA, IGN and provide links to download from that global/regional archive. Happy to be contacted to discuss further."

"The most beneficial group of people from this project will be those who want to touch geodetic data for the first time. It would be nice if it could be easily used in education/training purposes. However, I am not sure if this attempt is really worth our (primarily Martin's?) time and efforts especially because the task can be endless."

"Thanks Martin. I am unsure about what metadata we have and how it's handled."

"Thank you for your efforts"

"Sharing geodetic data through GGOS is an excellent initiative"

"Please also consider pointers to education, training and capacity building elements within IAG and other groups. The Geoid School is a good example where practical training occurs. Identifying this training opportunity would likewise be beneficial."

"Nice initiative!"

"It would be important to invite to contribute to the GGOS portal generators of geodetic observations and products, which are not directly linked to the IAG, but which follow the standards of the IAG (or its services). Somehow, the quality of the data to be linked to the GGOS portal should be evaluated and classified."

"It was not clear to me whether the portal would be an interface to data archives or a data archive itself."

"Ideally the portal should making finding and sharing geodetic products and data as easy as possible. Encourage DOIs and metadata but don't make them requirements that could discourage participation. Avoid complicated layers of security that make access difficult. Keep the portal as simple as possible."

"I would like to see the EGV (Essential geodetic variables) more advertised. The geodetic products should be linked to the EGVs. The GGOS Portal could be the place to provide such EGVs, maybe not only for scientists but also for manager/decision makers ..."

"I wish you continued success in serving humanity... Thank you very much (GGOS)"

"I think I have given them above; I think that it is more important to spend our efforts on securing the Geodetic Observing system including its infrastructure and stations/observatories, rather than work on an improved portal. But a nice/good description on various places where geodetic data and products may be found would be good information! I think that when UN-GGIM SCoG and GGCE are doing progress, I think that GGOS can make a big difference in working from the scientific perspective on Global Geodetic Infrastructure."

"I love the idea. I hope you can release it soon. I offer my help voluntarily for any task you need"

"I am a lead research on a project which aims to improve GNSS data and metadata delivery across spectrum of GNSS user sectors. as part of this work I am responsible for developing a standards (and the FAIR principles) compliant GNSS Metadata profile. the conceptual model of this profile is ready and we are about to implement the prototype. I am happy to connect with GGOS if there is an interest."

"I believe study of geodesy is very important to understand the Earth and the universe. when the humanity is facing challenges of climate change and global warming etc., this field has become more relevant now. It is interesting to see that all components of geodesy- the satellite geodesy, astronomy, geomagnetism etc. are so interrelated, more active study and research in these fields may show a path for solution of the pressing problems of today on the earth."

"Great initiative, fully aligned with GSSC goals (see <https://gssc.esa.int>) and our GNSS Digital Platform, GSSC Now (see <https://gssc.esa.int/now>). Feel free to reach out to me to identify collaboration opportunities."

"Get the participation first with a simple interface, advertise it, then develop and build from there. Don't get bogged down in details."

"Formal inquiries can be sent to national representatives in the IAG on how the geodetic community in a particular country can contribute to maintaining a single GGOS data portal and to express the general opinion with which they will contribute to the maintenance of such a portal"

“Creating such a survey is a good start for future improvements of GGOS. I appreciate the efforts of all contributors.”

“Congratulations on this initiative. It is very important for the community”

“Check out www.openaltimetry.org for a focused implementation of data discovery/viz/download for large altimetry datasets. The key to the popularity of the OA portal is its simplicity.”

“As I wrote, GGOS needs to do something useful first and then run surveys”

“As a researcher (and supervisor of graduate students) I would like to see GGOS Portal be a "go-to" when seeking authoritative data. The data itself need not be in the Portal, but the meta-data (and clear description of all aspects of the data, not just its source) should be.”

“- Data descriptions need to be much clearer for geological users who are not specialists in geodesy. There are so many models it is hard to find what dataset is the most suitable for structural geological and tectonics use (for me, mapping deep crustal and upper mantle features). Advantages and disadvantages should ideally be given. A comparison table of parameters and suitability for different purposes would make data selection easier, instead of long lists of models. - The current online visualisations do not show real uses of data. At least one final use image for geological purposes would help. - Ideally, data is required in several different formats, and especially available in at least one other format than .netcdf. So much geophysical data is available in netcdf format but some standard geophysical software cannot read this format, e.g. Seequent's Oasis Montaj (the main software used in N America by universities, geological surveys and mineral exploration companies) cannot read this data format.”

“GGOS is really a great project with great outlook. I would like to contribute”

“Looking forward more participation and collaboration with GGOS”